

A Comparative Analysis of Thermodynamic Efficiency Limits and Material Constraints in Modern

Turbofan Engines

DeLaney L. Kunkle

This research represents an independent student investigation in thermodynamics efficiency limits. While every effort was made to ensure accuracy, this paper is part of an early learning exploration of aerospace engineering concepts.

Thesis Statement

The second law of Thermodynamics will always cause real engines to operate below the ideal outcome, Carnot Limit. Though the Carnot Limit cannot be reached, not because of the engineer who makes the engines, but because of the irreversible processes such as heat waste, friction, and finite time operations which are unavoidable. If we can bypass the danger of these engines reaching extreme temperatures, we could ideally reach a higher efficiency than previously achievable. Mechanical energy can make heat, but the heat it creates is essentially unusable. The second law requires that there is some disorder that must remain as waste heat to prevent entropy from decreasing. Work can only be created when there is disorder to order, which means you need to force some random energy into a direction. That being said, you cannot convert the total amount of heat into work without rejecting some heat into a colder place.

Introduction

The aviation industry is responsible for a significant amount of carbon emissions, sharing roughly 2% of the world's CO₂ emissions. If we could limit this prolonged problem, that will only get worse. We could not only make jet engines more sustainable for the environment but also faster and less fuel consuming. Achieving these goals, however, requires more than just eliminating CO₂ emissions, we would need to eliminate or push the fundamental physical barriers preventing us from reaching a higher efficiency in these engines. To do this engines would need to operate dangerously high temperatures and pressures that push them closer to the Carnot Limit. But, this is a significant engineering challenge. Though, there have been some recent advancements in materials able to sustain these high demands, such as Ceramic Matrix Composites.

Principles of Thermodynamic Efficiency

The thermodynamic efficiency is how well the engine can convert heat into mechanical work, 2nd law of thermodynamics. These engines can be analyzed using Brayton's cycle. To observe the theoretical maximum efficiency, we need perfect circumstances. So, for the ideal Brayton Cycle, we need the working fluid to be assumed as a constant property, perfect gas that undergoes full expansion in the engine (turbine). The flow rate of mass is assumed constant, and there must be no bleeds. Under all these conditions, the ideal Brayton's cycle, the maximum efficiency, can be expressed as, $1 - \left(\frac{p_3}{p_2}\right)^{\frac{(1-\gamma)}{\gamma}}$, γ being the ratio of specific heats.

Thermal vs. Propulsive Efficiency Analysis

$$\eta = \frac{W_{net}}{Q_{in}} \quad \eta = \frac{2V_0}{V_e + V_0}$$

Propulsive efficiency is how effectively a propulsion system can turn power from the engine into a useful thrust. But this process always produces waste energy. When the exhaust shoots out, it's usually faster than the aircraft actually needs; this is what creates the waste. Thermal efficiency tells you how much of all the heat energy from fuel; what of that was actually conveyed into useful work. But because of the second law of Thermodynamics, no engine can turn 100% of the heat energy into work. A combination of these systems can be modeled as, $\eta_0 = \eta_{th} \cdot \eta_p$

Research Questions

- Why does the Second Law of Thermodynamics prevent jet engines from being 100% efficient?
- How do engineers balance the trade off between the weight of the engine and heat management?
- Is there a relationship between Compressor Pressure Ratio (CPR) and engine performance and what is it?

Theoretical Framework

The Brayton's Cycle Model

Brayton's Cycle helps scientists explain how turbine engines create energy, basically a repeating process where heat turns into motion/work. There are four steps to this cycle: Compression, when air comes in from the outside, the compressor squeezes into a smaller space, causing the temperature to rise.

Combustion is the step where fuel is added to the already heated air. This causes the air to get hotter and expand. Expansion, hot air rushes out, and the turbines are pushed. This is where the energy comes out and goes back into the compressors. Exhaust, this is where the air that has done its work leaves the engine and blasts out the back of the jet as thrust. Temperature, pressure and volume all relate through gas laws (Like, $PV=nRT$). During this cycle, some heat is lost; this is called waste heat. This image depicts the process.

$PV=nRT$, Pressure (P), Volume (V), and Temperature (T). This formula helps us understand what happens when the air is compressed. “Isentropic”= This is a theoretical perfect efficiency, which happens when no heat is lost. “Adiabatic” = No heat enters or leaves during compression or expansion. This is relevant because no real engines are perfectly isentropic or adiabatic, which means it lowers efficiency. Because metal components can take only so much heat, cooling systems are put in place, but this makes the aircraft heavier and more complex.

Systematic Efficiency and Trade-offs

Both Propulsive and Thermal efficiency must be good for the engine to be efficient overall. If an engine has great thermal efficiency, but shoots out at a very high velocity, it creates waste of the thermal energy, making it inefficient overall. Which makes the reverse also true; the overall efficiency informs you of the fuel effectiveness of the propulsion system.

Turbojets:

- High exhaust velocity → Low propulsive efficiency
- Moderate thermal efficiency → Low overall efficiency

High-bypass Turbofans:

- Moderate-high thermal efficiency → Moderate overall efficiency
- Very high propulsive efficiency → Highest overall efficiency

Rockets:

- High exhaust velocity → Very low propulsive efficiency
- High thermal efficiency → Low overall efficiency, thrust prioritized

Primary Constraints on Engine Efficiency

Compressor Pressure Ratio (CPR) Effects

The compressor pressure ratio (CPR) is a measure of air compression. A higher pressure ratio means better efficiency of the engine. Many modern engines can achieve ratios of 40:1 or higher. CPR can be ultimately defined as the ratio of pressure at the compressor discharge and the compressor inlet. An increase in the CPR would be an increase in the power turbine pressure ratio.

Turbine Inlet Temperature (TIT) Limits

The Turbine Inlet Temperature (TIT) is the temperature of which the combustion gases are when they enter the first stage of the turbine. These temperatures are not exactly measured from the heat, because it can reach such an extreme level, over 17000 degrees Celsius. But when these temperatures can be measured, it is by a number of thermocouples that are in the exhaust stream. The measurement is presented on the flight deck in either Fahrenheit or Celsius. The TIT can be limited by material strength and the resistance of the turbine blades. Materials able to operate under higher temperatures lead to higher efficiency.

Conclusion

There is a constant pursuit for a turbofan engine perfectly efficient; it's a battle against the fundamental laws of physics and defies things most would perceive as impossible. Validated by the Second Law of Thermodynamics, the perfect efficiency is "Carnot Limit," which, alas, is only theoretical; real-world engines can never truly reach this boundary due to friction and waste heat. Though engineers push the boundary everyday of what we know and continue to assimilate the Brayton Cycles. Advancements in materials such as Ceramic Matrix Composites can make it possible for the aviation industry to increase its Compressor Pressure Ratio and Turbine Inlet Temperature, all while reducing its carbon footprint. While it's possible we may never attain the Carnot Limit, heat resistant ceramics offer a viable path forward.

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